

was quite perceptible when the reaction mixture was acidified with aqueous HCl (6 N). The oily mass was washed thoroughly with water and then triturated several times with petroleum ether followed by ethanol, when a yellow solid was obtained. It was dried, washed with diethyl ether and crystallised from ethanol/glacial acetic acid, m.p. 178° (2a).

The ethereal washings on evaporation afforded a small amount of a pale yellow product, crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 203° (4a).

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References

1. R. T. JADHAV and M. G. PARANJPE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 1003.
2. V. K. VERMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 300.
3. C. P. JOSEPH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 37, 621.
4. R. MAYER in 'Organic Chemistry of Sulphur', ed. S. OAE, Plenum Press, New York, 1977, pp. 41, 45.
5. V. K. VERMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 116.

Application of Chlorotrimethylsilane. Reaction of Bromonitroolefins with Chlorotrimethylsilane

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RECENT publications¹⁻³ have highlighted diverse utility of chlorotrimethylsilane (ClMe₃Si) as an important reagent for organic synthesis. This reagent can be used either directly or in combination with a suitable metal. The versatile nature of chlorotrimethylsilane in chemical transformations prompted us to carry out the reaction of 3β-acetoxy-7α-bromo-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1)⁴, 3β-chloro-7α-bromo-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (2)⁴ and 4β,7α-dibromo-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (3)⁴ with chlorotrimethylsilane in presence of zinc dust which gave 3β-acetoxy-5α-cholestan-6-one (4), 3β-chloro-5α-cholestan-6-one (5) and 5α-cholestan-6-one (6), respectively in excellent yield. Our study showed that chlorotrimethylsilane reduces the olefinic nitro group present in ring 'B' of steroids to ketone and debromination also takes place from C₇ and C₄ positions.

	X	R ₁	R ₂		X
1	OAc	H	Br	4	OAc
2	Cl	H	Br	5	Cl
3	H	Br	Br	6	H

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Varian A60 instrument using TMS as an internal standard.

Reaction of chlorotrimethylsilane and zinc dust with steroidal compounds 1 to 3: A typical procedure is described for 1. To a solution of 3β-acetoxy-7α-bromo-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1)⁴ (2 g) in ether (100 ml) was added chlorotrimethylsilane (10 ml). To this mixture, zinc dust (6 g) was added in small portions over a period of 30 min. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 4 h at room temperature (the progress of the reaction was checked through tlc). At the completion of the reaction, zinc dust was filtered and the solution was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution (2%) and water. Ether layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent gave 3β-acetoxy-5α-cholestan-6-one (4) which was crystallised from alcohol (1.70 g), m.p. and m.m.p. 127° (lit.⁵ 127°).

Similar treatment of 2 (2 g) with zinc dust (6 g) and chlorotrimethylsilane (10 ml) gave 3β-chloro-5α-cholestan-6-one (5) (1.75 g), m.p. and m.m.p. 128° (lit.⁶ 129°).

The compound (3) (2 g) similarly provided the expected 5α-cholestan-6-one (6) (1.7 g), m.p. and m.m.p. 97° (lit.⁷ 98°).

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References

1. W. B. MOTHERWELL, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1978, 935.
2. P. HODGE and M. N. KHAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1975, 809.
3. C. BURDFORD, F. COOKE, E. EHLINGER and P. MAGNUS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 99, 4536.

4. SHAFIULLAH, S. HUSAIN, H. ALI, H. OGURA and H. TAKAYANAGI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, **22**, 71.
5. R. M. DODSON and B. REIGEL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1948, **13**, 424.
6. A. WINDAUS and O. DALMER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1919, **52**, 162.
7. C. W. SHOPPÉE, D. N. JONES, J. R. LEWIS and G. H. R. SUMMERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2876.

***N*-Aryl-*N*-acetylureido-*O*-alkylxanthates and Bis[*N*-aryl-*N*'-acetylureido]-*O*-polymethylene Bisanthates**

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A large number of salts of *O*-alkylxanthic acid have been reported to exhibit fungicidal activity^{1,2}. The benzyl ester of butylxanthate is used as insecticide for red spider³. Halogenopolynitro aryl esters of *O*-methyl- and *O*-ethylxanthic acid have been synthesised and screened for their fungicidal activity by Gupta *et al.*⁴. Chloroacetylcarbamides possessing insecticidal activities were described by Hoegberg *et al.*⁵. It was, therefore, considered of interest to condense chloroacetylcarbamides with potassium-*O*-alkylxanthates to obtain *N*-aryl-*N*'-acetylureido-*O*-alkylxanthates (1). In addition, chloroacetylcarbamides were also condensed with dipotassium-*O*-polymethylene bisxanthates to obtain bis[*N*-aryl-*N*'-acetylureido]-*O*-polymethylene bisxanthates (2). All these compounds were screened for their antifungal activity.

TABLE 1—*N*-ARYL-*N*'-ACETYLUREIDO-*O*-ALKYLXANTHATES (1)^a

Compd no	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C
R' = OH,			
1	H	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	118
2 ^b	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	151
3.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	145-46
4.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	135
5	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	165-66
6.	<i>p</i> -Br	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ BrN ₂ O ₃ S ₂	145
7	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₃ S ₂	146-47
R = C _n H _{2n} ,			
8	H	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	124
9	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	213-14
10.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	152-53
11	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	110
12.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	134
13.	<i>p</i> -Br	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ O ₃ S ₂	144
14. ^c	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₃ S ₂	161

^aAll the compounds were obtained in 70-80% yield, and they gave satisfactory N, S analyses.

^b $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3200 (NH), 1710 (NHCONH), 1592, 1500 (C=O, aromatic), 1400 (CH₂CO), 1245 (O-N, stretch), 1170 (C=S) and 765 (1,2-disubstituted benzene ring) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.0 (2H, s, COCH₂), 4.1 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7-7.5 (4H, m, ArH), 7.8 (1H, s, NHAr) and 10.2 (1H, s, CONHCO).

^c $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3210 (NH), 1700 (NHCONH), 1600, 1500 (C=O, aromatic), 1410 (CH₂CO), 1265 (O-N, stretch), 1190 (C=S) and 840 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.4 (3H, t, CH₃), 4 (2H, s, COCH₂), 4.6 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.1-7.5 (5H, m, 4ArH+NH) and 10.35 (1H, s, CONHCO).

Potassium salts of xanthic acids were prepared from methanol, ethanol, ethanediol and propane-1,3-diol by their reaction with carbon disulphide and KOH⁷.

N-Aryl-*N*'-acetylureido-*O*-alkylxanthates (1) and bis[*N*-aryl-*N*'-acetylureido]-*O*-polymethylene bisxanthates (2): A solution of potassium-*O*-alkylxanthate (0.02 mol) or dipotassium-*O*-polymethylene bisxanthate (0.01 mol) in 40 ml of acetone was

Experimental

Substituted phenylcarbamides and their corresponding chloroacetyl derivatives were prepared according to the methods reported earlier⁶.

added to a suspension of appropriate chloroacetyl-*N*-substituted phenylcarbamides (0.02 mol) in 50 ml of acetone. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and then refluxed for 2 h. The cooled reaction mixture was filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The solid

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